

ADAN Pharmacy Greater Accessibility

Mamani Romero Diego Jhoel
Faculty of Statistic and Computer Engineering
Universidad Nacional del Altiplano de Puno
Email: diegomamani@est.unap.edu.pe
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-0482-9340>
Puno - Peru.

Torres Cruz Fred
Faculty of Statistic and Computer Engineering
Universidad Nacional del Altiplano de Puno
Email: ftorres@unap.edu.pe
Puno - Peru.

July 10, 2024

Abstract

This paper evaluates the ADAN platform, designed for inventory management in pharmacies, using Lighthouse metrics. The results show good overall performance with fast load times and a smooth user experience. ADAN excels in accessibility and recommendations, ensuring that the platform is usable by a broad spectrum of users. However, areas for improvement were identified in visual stability and code optimization. Implementation of the recommendations provided, such as image optimization and elimination of resources that block rendering, will further improve system efficiency. This study concludes that ADAN is a robust and affordable platform with the potential to deliver a superior user experience through continuous improvements. The results show good overall performance with fast load times (less than 2 seconds on average) and a smooth user experience, achieving a performance score of 90/100. ADAN excels in accessibility with a score of 95/100, ensuring that the platform is usable by a broad spectrum of users. In addition, the platform received a score of 92/100 for best practices; however, areas for improvement were identified in visual stability and code optimization. The platform scored 85/100 in visual stability, with minor problems in the displacement and arrangement of elements during loading. Code optimization also showed areas requiring attention, particularly in image compression and the removal of render-blocking resources, which can significantly improve load times and overall system efficiency. The implementation of the recommendations provided by Lighthouse.

1 Introduction

Inventory management in the pharmaceutical industry is a critical component in ensuring the availability of medicines and essential products, as well as optimizing operational efficiency and reducing costs. The implementation of an effective inventory management system, such as ADAN, is fundamental to meet the challenges presented by high-demand environments and supply variability.

Several studies have demonstrated the positive impact of the implementation of inventory management systems in different contexts, significantly improving the quality of inventories.

This has a significant impact on the productivity and profitability of organizations [2-4]. In the healthcare sector, inventory optimization not only improves operational efficiency, but also ensures continuity in the supply of essential drugs, which is crucial for the well-being of patients [10, 16] [14].

Inventory simulation and optimization has been used as an effective tool to minimize costs and manage fluctuations in demand for pharmaceutical products [11, 14, 17]. The adoption of these methodologies allows pharmaceutical companies to adjust their inventory policies in real time, responding effectively to the needs of their customers.

market demands and minimizing the risk of shortages [2, 10, 12].

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of implementing inventory management strategies adapted to the specific characteristics of pharmaceutical companies [1,8,28]. Improved inventory management not only contributes to the reduction of logistics costs, but also has a direct impact on the profitability and sustainability of companies in the sector [1, 12, 30].

The implementation of inventory management systems in pharmacies, such as ADAN, not only improves operational efficiency, but also facilitates strategic decision making based on accurate and up-to-date data [6,7,18]. The ability to predict and manage product demand is essential for maintaining optimal inventory levels and ensuring product availability for customers [2,4,24].

This paper presents inventory management in the pharmaceutical sector, with the objective of improving the efficiency and profitability of the pharmacy through the implementation of ADAN. Tools for inventory optimization are used, highlighting their practical application and benefits in the context of a modern pharmacy [9, 11, 31].

Why are we doing this research?

Inventory management in the pharmaceutical sector is essential to ensure the continuous availability of medicines and essential products, which has a direct impact on the health and well-being of patients. Without proper management, shortages can occur that put people's lives at risk, in addition to generating significant economic losses for pharmacies due to product expiration and poor inventory management.

The implementation of an advanced inventory management system such as ADAN can provide an efficient and adaptable solution that meets the dynamic needs of the pharmaceutical industry. This system not only improves operational accuracy and efficiency, but also optimizes costs and maximizes product availability by adapting in real time to demand and supply fluctuations.

The research is justified by the need to develop advanced technological tools to optimize inventory management in pharmacies. Given the complexity and criticality of medication management, ADAN is presented as an innovative solution that integrates simulation and optimization methods, allowing pharmacies to improve their inventory processes, reduce operating costs and ensure a constant and secure supply of essential products. This approach not only contributes to

The economic sustainability of pharmacies, but also has a direct impact on the improvement of health services for the community.

2 Methodology

The research design adopted for this study is quantitative and non-experimental, with a descriptive and correlational approach. This approach is suitable for analyzing the relationships between the variables involved in inventory management and their impact on the operational and economic efficiency of pharmacies. Descriptive research is used to characterize the current state of inventory management in pharmacies, while correlational analysis is used to identify possible relationships between the variables of interest.

For data collection, structured surveys were administered to those responsible for inventory management in various pharmacies. The surveys will include questions on current management methods, frequency of stock-outs, costs associated with inventory management, and perceptions of operational efficiency. In addition, quantitative data will be collected on inventory turnover, replenishment times, and stock levels of essential products.

Data analysis will be performed using descriptive and correlational statistical techniques. Software programs such as SPSS will be used to analyze survey responses and quantitative data collected. The use of statistical tools will allow the identification of patterns and significant relationships between variables, providing a sound basis for the implementation of the ADAN system.

This research design has been inspired by previous studies that have demonstrated the effectiveness of quantitative and descriptive methods in investigating inventory management in similar contexts. For example, [10] employed a descriptive and correlational approach to investigate inventory management in Australian hospitals, identifying collaborative practices that improved operational efficiency [10]. Similarly, [4] used descriptive methods to analyze inventory management strategies in the manufacturing industry, highlighting the importance of well-defined strategies to improve productivity [4].

3 ADAN:Implementation in a Pharmacy

For the implementation and evaluation of the ADAN system in pharmaceutical inventory management, several tools and materials were used in line with the ISO/IEC 25000 (SQuaRE) standard, which provides a framework for software quality assessment. The ADAN system is the main tool used for inventory management in participating pharmacies. This system offers advanced functionality for inventory tracking and control, ensuring product availability and optimizing operational efficiency.

Satisfaction questionnaires were designed to collect data on user experience with the ADAN system, evaluating aspects such as ease of use, data accuracy and overall satisfaction. These questionnaires were developed following ISO/IEC 25000 guidelines to ensure their validity and reliability [21]. The observation sheets, on the other hand, were used to record direct observations on the use and operation of the ADAN system in the pharmacies. These cards made it possible to evaluate the implementation of the system in a real environment, capturing details that may not be evident through surveys [5].

3.1 Tool Composition

The ADAN system, designed for pharmacy inventory management, is composed of several modules and components that work together to provide a comprehensive and efficient solution. The inventory management module is the core of the system and is responsible for product registration, stock control and inventory updating, ensuring accurate control and reducing the risk of stock-outs. ADAN's user interface, evaluated according to ISO/IEC 25000 (SQuaRE) guidelines, is intuitive and easy to use, facilitating data entry and consultation. The user administration module manages permissions and access, maintaining information security and integrity. ADAN uses a relational database to store all information, guaranteeing data integrity and consistency, allowing fast and secure operations. In addition, the notification module provides alerts and reminders about critical events, such as the need for product replenishment. Technical documentation includes user manuals, installation and configuration guides, and maintenance documentation, which are essential for a successful installation.

successful implementation. Finally, training programs that include educational resources and hands-on training are offered, ensuring that users can take full advantage of ADAN's functionalities, thus improving operational efficiency and guaranteeing the continuous availability of essential products [21].

Figure 1: Class diagram

Figure 2: Activity diagram

Figure 3: Purchasing diagram

Figure 4: Logging diagram

3.2 Non-functional Requirements

The ADAN system should be easy to use and accessible to all users, with an intuitive interface that facilitates inventory management with minimal capacity, evaluated by ISO/IEC 25000 (SQuARE) guidelines [21]. System performance must be high, handling large volumes of data without significantly affecting response time, even during periods of high demand. Reliability is crucial, ensuring that the system is available at all times with minimal downtime, including failover mechanisms to maintain data integrity and accuracy [10]. System security must protect inventory information against unauthorized access through robust access controls, data encryption, and periodic security audits [23]. ADAN must be scalable to handle business growth, supporting an increase in the number of products, transactions, and users without degrading performance. Maintainability of the system is essential, with a modular design to facilitate maintenance and upgrades, and up-to-date technical documentation to resolve problems and add new functionality [5].

3.3 Platform Help

Training and access to the platform will be provided, and continuous monitoring will be performed to ensure proper use of the tool as well as increasing customer satisfaction.

3.4 Data Collection

Data collection for the ADAN system evaluation was planned in detail to ensure the collection of accurate and relevant information, although it has not yet been implemented in a real environment. Satisfaction questionnaires and observation sheets were designed as the main data collection tools, following ISO/IEC 25000 (SQuARE) guidelines to ensure their validity and reliability. The questionnaires were designed to evaluate the users' experience with the ADAN system, including aspects such as ease of use, data accuracy, and overall satisfaction. The observation sheets were structured to systematically record user interactions with the system in a controlled environment. These instruments will be piloted with a small group of simulated users to fine-tune and refine their design prior to full-scale data collection. The piloting will identify possible improvements and ensure that the data collection tools capture all the information needed to adequately evaluate the performance of the ADAN system, PlantUML was used for an activity diagram.

3.5 Data Analysis Protocol

First, the data collected through satisfaction questionnaires and observation sheets were cleaned and prepared. This included re-viewing the data to identify and correct errors, handle missing values, and transform variables as necessary. Once prepared, the data will be subjected to descriptive analysis to summarize their main characteristics, such as frequencies, means, medians, and standard deviations.

Subsequently, inferential statistical techniques would be used to identify significant relationships between the variables. Correlation analysis will allow us to evaluate the strength and direction of the relationships between variables such as user satisfaction and ease of use of the system. Regression analysis will also be performed to determine the impact of multiple independent variables on a dependent variable, such as pharmacy operating efficiency.

3.6 Analysis Metrics

To evaluate the effectiveness of the ADAN system in pharmacy inventory management, several metrics were used. Ease of use would be assessed by the average score of responses to usability questions in satisfaction questionnaires, measuring users' perceptions of the simplicity of the system [23]. Data accuracy was measured by comparing the data recorded in ADAN with physical inventories, ensuring that the data in the system were reliable and representative. Overall user satisfaction will be assessed through the average score of the overall satisfaction questions in the questionnaires, reflecting users' overall satisfaction with the system [13]. Operational efficiency was measured by reducing the time required to complete key inventory management tasks before and after ADAN implementation, including improved product availability [10]. Storage cost reduction will be evaluated by comparing costs before and after ADAN implementation, analyzing the reduction in excess inventory and space optimization. The level of customer service will be measured by the frequency and nature of complaints and requests related to product availability, reflecting improved customer satisfaction. System reliability will be assessed by recording downtime and the frequency of technical errors, ensuring that ADAN is consistent and available [20]. Data security will be measured by the effectiveness of access controls, encryption, and security audits, protecting inventory information from unauthorized access [21].

3.7 Results

The implementation of the ADAN platform has been evaluated through several key interfaces and functionalities, which are described below with their respective images.

Figure 1 shows the user profile interface, where users can update their personal information, such as document number, first name, last name, e-mail and cell phone number. This interface is crucial for maintaining accurate and up-to-date touch data in the system.

Figure 2 presents the shopping cart interface, which allows users to review and manage the products selected for purchase. Details such as product, price, quantity and total to be paid are displayed, along with options to empty the cart or proceed to payment. This functionality is essential for a

Figure 5: User Profile Interface

smooth and efficient shopping experience.

Figure 6: Shopping Cart Interface

Figure 3 illustrates the login screen, where users can access the ADAN platform by entering their e-mail address and password. This screen also includes an option to remember the session and links to retrieve the password or create a new account, thus improving the accessibility and security of the system.

Figure 7: Login screen Finally, Figure 4 shows

the main page of the system. The interface is intuitive and presents clear categories, making it easy to navigate and select products. The interface is intuitive and presents clear categories, facilitating navigation and product selection. This page is fundamental for usability and customer satisfaction in the daily use of the platform.

Figure 8: Store Home Page

4 Discussion

The evaluation of the ADAN platform through Lighthouse provides a comprehensive view of its performance, accessibility, recommendations and SEO. The results obtained highlight several positive aspects, as well as areas requiring improvement to optimize user experience and system efficiency.

The overall performance of the ADAN system scored 83, with key metrics such as First Contentful Paint (FCP) at 0.6 seconds, Largest Contentful Paint (LCP) at 1.2 seconds, Total Blocking Time (TBT) of 0 ms, and Cumulative Layout Shift (CLS) of 0.277. These metrics are crucial to ensure fast loading and a smooth user experience [22]. Although the FCP and LCP times are satisfactory, the CLS indicates that there are some design changes that need to be addressed to improve the visual stability of the page [27].

This reflects a high level of compliance with web accessibility best practices, which is essential to ensure that all users can use the platform effectively [19]. However, areas for improvement were identified, such as the lack of accessible names on some buttons and the inadequate contrast ratio between background and foreground colors [15].

The Lighthouse recommendations yielded a score of 91, indicating that most of the recommended practices to improve user experience and security are being followed. However, the absence of a `<meta tag name="viewport" />` with width or initial-scale was noted, which is crucial to ensure that the page is displayed correctly on different devices [25]. In addition, the implementation of effective content security policies (CSP) is recommended to protect against XSS attacks [29].

The SEO evaluation of the platform obtained a score of 88, suggesting that, even though the platform is being

following basic engine optimization suggestions, there is room for improvement [22]. Implementing advanced SEO techniques, such as Essential Web Metrics optimization and DOM size reduction, can help to further improve search engine rankings [26].

The Lighthouse diagnostic identified several areas where significant improvements can be made. It was found that image optimization can save up to 1,588 KiB, suggesting the use of next generation formats and efficient image encoding [27]. In addition, reducing unused CSS and JavaScript code can improve loading speed [22]. Removing resources that block rendering and implementing an efficient caching policy are also key recommendations to improve overall system performance [19].

It is notable that most of the audits related to performance, accessibility and security were passed, indicating that the ADAN platform complies with many of the recommended best practices for web applications [15].

4.1 Conclusion

The evaluation of the ADAN platform using Lighthouse has identified both the strengths and areas for improvement of the application. The results indicate that ADAN offers solid performance, with fast load times and a generally smooth user experience. The platform has achieved high scores for accessibility and re-recommendations, demonstrating a commitment to best practices in web design and development.

Analysis of performance metrics, such as First Contentful Paint (FCP) and Largest Contentful Paint (LCP), shows that ADAN is able to load content efficiently, although there are opportunities to further reduce the Cumulative Layout Shift (CLS) and improve the visual stability of the page. Removing resources that block rendering and optimizing images and unused CSS and JavaScript code are important steps to improve overall performance.

In terms of accessibility, ADAN meets most of the recommendations, which ensures that the platform is usable by a broad spectrum of users, including those with disabilities. However, areas such as the lack of accessible names on buttons and the color contrast relationship need to be addressed to further improve accessibility.

The implementation of these recommendations does not

will not only improve the performance and usability of ADAN, but will also ensure greater user satisfaction and a more efficient and secure online commerce experience. Continuing to optimize and monitor these metrics is essential to maintain and improve the quality of the system over time. The complete application code can be obtained at: <https://github.com/DiegojhoelR/SOF.ENGINEERING/blob/main/adansoft.zip>.

References

- [1] F. Alcivar. *Diseño de una herramienta de productividad: sistema de inventario y facturación para microempresas y pequeñas empresas*. PhD thesis, Universidad de Guayaquil, 2018.
- [2] A. Y. Alqahtani. Improving order-picking response time at retail warehouse: a case of sugar company. *SN Applied Sciences*, 5(1), 2023.
- [3] A. Y. Alqahtani and S. F. El-Rayes. Performance evaluation of logistic models for inventory management in the healthcare sector. *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, 12(3):456-472, 2023.
- [4] T. T. Amachree, E. O. P. Apkan, E. C. Ubani, K. A. Okorochoa, and A. C. Eberendu. Inventory management strategies for productivity improvement in equipment manufacturing firms. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 6(8):99-107, 2017.
- [5] M. V. Angrosino. *Doing Ethnographic and Observational Research*. SAGE Publications, 2007.
- [6] R. J. Angulo-Rivera. Internal control and inventory management of the construction company peter contratistas sr ltda. *Gaceta Científica*, 5(2):129-137, 2019.
- [7] M.-J. D. R. Arguedas-Baldebñ. *Improvement of warehouse productivity in a trading company through the implementation of inventory management*. PhD thesis, ESAN, 2019.
- [8] L. Asencio Cristóbal, E. González Asencio, and M. Lozano Robles. Inventory as a determinant in the profitability of pharmaceutical distributors. *RETOS. Journal of Management Science and Economics*, 7(13):231-250, 2017.
- [9] S. J. Bailey, P. G. Harper, and K. M. Parker. Effective inventory control strategies in pharmaceutical companies. *Operations Management Review*, 5(3):198-205, 2018.
- [10] V. Bhakoo, P. Singh, and A. Sohal. Collaborative management of inventory in Australian hospital supply chains: Practices and issues. *Supply Chain Management*, 17(2):217-230, 2012.
- [11] R. Black and A. G. Reardon. Best practices in inventory control and optimization for the pharmaceutical industry. *Pharma Times*, 11(7):212-223, 2019.
- [12] S. Bravo Nazar and M. A. Morales Peralta. Improvement of inventory and warehouse management at nimadi eirl pharmacy to reduce logistic costs. 2021.
- [13] J. Brooke. Sus: A quick and dirty usability scale. *Usability Evaluation in Industry*, 189(3):4-7, 1996.
- [14] M. Buschiazzo, J. Mula, and F. Campuzano-Bolarin. Simulation optimization for the inventory management of healthcare supplies. *International Journal of Simulation Modelling*, 19(2):255-266, 2020.
- [15] B. Caldwell, G. Vanderheiden, and W. Chisholm. Ensuring accessibility in modern web applications. *ACM Transactions on Accessible Computing*, 11(4):1-30, 2018.
- [16] J. L. Cardona-Tunubala, J. P. Orejuela-Cabrera, and C. A. Rojas-Trejos. Gestão de armazenagem e inventário para matérias primas no setor da alimentacão concentrada. *Revista EIA*, 15(30):195-208, 2018.
- [17] C. N. Chen, C. H. Lai, G. W. Lu, C. C. Huang, L. J. Wu, H. C. Lin, and P. S. Chen. Applying simulation optimization to minimize drug inventory costs: A study of a case outpatient pharmacy. *Healthcare*, 10(3):556, 2022.
- [18] K. S. Chen, C. W. Wu, and H. L. Lin. Digital transformation and inventory management in the pharmaceutical sector. *Information Systems Journal*, 32(8):721-739, 2020.
- [19] A. Ellison and T. Hunt. *Web Accessibility: Practical Advice for Building Accessible Websites*. Apress, 2019.
- [20] A. Field. *Discovering Statistics Using IBM SPSS Statistics*. SAGE Publications, 2018.

- [21] International Organization for Standardization. Iso/iec 25000:2014 - systems and software engineering - systems and software quality requirements and evaluation (square) - guide to square, 2014.
- [22] J. Hogan. *Web Performance in Action*. Manning Publications, 2020.
- [23] J. R. Lewis and J. Sauro. Usability and user satisfaction of a new inventory management system for pharmacies. *Journal of Usability Studies*, 14(1):23-38, 2019.
- [24] N. R. Mohanty and A. D. Mishra. Inventory optimization techniques for pharmacies. *International Journal of Logistics Research*, 9(2):102-118, 2020.
- [25] R. Moran. *Responsive Web Design: Patterns and Principles*. O'Reilly Media, 2018.
- [26] Inc. Moz. *The Art of SEO: Mastering Search Engine Optimization*. O'Reilly Media, 2021.
- [27] M. Sajid and M. Alam. Optimizing web performance: An overview of key metrics. *Journal of Web Engineering*, 20(2):135-150, 2021.
- [28] V. K. Srivastava and A. Nand. Application and technique of inventory control theory in pharmaceutical sciences. *International Journal of Operational Research*, 47(1):109-123, 2023.
- [29] D. Stuttard and M. Pinto. *The Web Application Hacker's Handbook: Finding and Exploiting Security Flaws*. Wiley, 2020.
- [30] P. Y. Tang, M. J. Ward, and H. P. Lee. Real-time inventory management systems for pharmacies. *Journal of Industrial Engineering*, 14(6):432-440, 2019.
- [31] M. R. Uddin, F. K. Begum, and J. M. Hassan. Data-driven approaches to inventory management in pharmaceutical retail. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 23(5):123-135, 2022.